

MINORITY REPORT

Minority Report: Public Engagement Dublin – Round 1

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Executive summary

The report summarises the first round of engagement activities conducted for the Minority Report project in the Dublin case study site: Ringsend and Poolbeg. Two different activities were held on 14 May 2025, at the Ringsend and Irishtown Community Centre. The first activity took the form of a discussion-based workshop with potential end-users of the Minority Report tool, including urban planners, academics, and policymakers working on urban risk resilience in Dublin. Participants discussed data requirements for the tool, the potential benefits and limitations of the platform, critical and vulnerable infrastructure in the case study area, as well as community needs and behaviours during emergency climate events, from their respective professional perspectives. The second activity consisted of an open-to-all community festival in the afternoon with various stands hosted by relevant project researchers to similarly discuss with citizens their needs and behaviours during climate related events and to better understand their lived experiences in the neighbourhood. 28 individuals were engaged over the course of the two engagement activities and at least double were indirectly exposed to information about the project through the community festival. The data collected throughout the activities will be analysed by the relevant project partners and integrated into their research streams. The main learnings from the engagement activities are also integrated throughout the following report, helping inform and prepare the project for the future rounds of engagement, not just in Dublin but also in the remaining other case study sites.

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1 Introduction

Engagement is a cornerstone of the Minority Report (MR) project. Continuous rounds of engagement over the course of the project's duration will give MR partners the possibility to exchange knowledge, and experiences with stakeholders relevant to their research, ensuring that the project's final product effectively meets stakeholder requirements, capacities, and needs, thereby maximising its long-term impact. The project's engagement focuses on two streams of stakeholders: local stakeholders and potential end-users of the MR technology platform.

The following report documents the first round of engagement activities conducted with both categories of stakeholders in the Dublin case study site: Ringsend and Irishtown. The main objectives of the first round of engagement, as defined in close collaboration with relevant MR partners, were the following:

1. Verify technical requirements of the MR tool with end-users
2. Identify critical and vulnerable infrastructure in the case study area
3. Discuss relevant governance structures, decision-making processes and alert systems
4. Identify social and behavioural characteristics within the case study area

To reach each objective, different activities were designed to ensure they would be tailored to the research needs as well as to the local Dublin context. For this first round, engagement with end-users took the form of a discussion-based workshop with relevant Dublin-based policymakers, academics, and urban planners alongside key project partners. Engagement with community members was organised as a small community 'festival' in collaboration with the neighbourhood's community centre, involving various activities, food, and entertainment that would encourage a diverse group of citizens from the neighbourhood to participate.

2 End-user engagement

2.1 Event details

The first engagement with potential end-users of the Minority Report technology platform took place at the Ringsend and Irishtown Community Centre on 14 May 2025, between 11 am and 1 pm. It took the shape of input presentations, including an introduction to the project and the vision for the technology platform, and active discussions around several core topics: the technology platform, the critical infrastructure in the case study area and the social vulnerabilities during extreme events. The agenda of the event can be found in Annex 1.

The event was organized by Dublin City Council (DCC) in close collaboration with Prospex Institute (PI) and with contributions from Integrated Environmental Solutions (IES) und University College London (UCL). All organisations are partners in the Minority Report project.

The workshop was attended by eight participants. Each attendee was classified according to the relevant end-user stakeholder category they felt they belonged to. Overall, there were three participants from the “Built environment”, three from “Government”, and two that were classified as “Other”, both working in academia related fields.

2.2 Event proceedings

2.2.1 Introduction

The workshop opened with Sabrina Dekker from Dublin City Council (DCC) setting the stage by contextualizing the MR project under the broader national climate action framework in Dublin. She emphasized the role of local authorities in developing Dublin’s **Decarbonisation Zone (DZ)**, the project’s Dublin case study area, particularly in areas identified as critical due to their infrastructure density and heightened flood risk. This location was strategically chosen for its vulnerability and importance, highlighting the need for targeted resilience planning. Sabrina also pointed out that the project aligns with other European efforts in the area; in addition to the MR project, there is one more EU-funded project focusing on similar thematic areas called [REGEN](#).

Following Sabrina’s introduction, Katharina Faradsch from Prospex Institute (PI) took the floor to outline the structure of the workshop and its key objectives, giving participants a clear roadmap of the sessions to understand the flow of activities and expected outcomes. Gabrielle Froes from PI then facilitated a brief icebreaker to foster interaction and ease participants into the co-creative atmosphere of the event.

With the room warmed up, Niall Buckley from Integrated Environmental Services (IES) introduced the MR project from a research and technical perspective, explaining that its aim is to optimize built infrastructure in the face of climate-related threats, and, in the Dublin case study site, particularly the one of flooding. He underscored that in Dublin, flood risk is considered the most pressing of the natural disasters the city faces. He described how data will be gathered from local pilot sites through Internet-of-Things (IoT) infrastructure and walked participants through various phases of the project. He also showcased an example of a digital platform from Nottingham City Council, which participants could consider a preliminary design of the MR digital platform, offering a glimpse into how it will function. A highlight of the tool is its 3D mapping feature, which visually demonstrates how the platform will identify critical infrastructure most at risk through various data inputs. This provided a tangible sense of how the MR technology platform will be able to support resilience-building efforts in vulnerable urban zones. Overall, the platform seeks to intuitively and accurately demonstrate where the risks in

the case study's-built environment are and, in doing so, show how various risks may have knock-on effects.

2.2.2 Session 1: Minority Report Technology Platform

Following the introductory presentations, participants were invited to share their doubts, concerns, and general impressions. Through these initial reactions and questions, the workshop moved into its planned discussion session 1, focusing specifically on end-user requirements and wishes for the technology platform.

Key points that emerged throughout the session are summarised below.

Key aims and benefits of the platform

The tools' purpose as a tool for **planning** was clarified and stressed. A participant mentioned that the tool would be especially beneficial for **major emergency planning**.

The importance of **inter-disciplinary** and **inter-sectoral collaboration** was highlighted by several participants. It was agreed that the tool's key value lies in its aim to **address risk** from **different perspectives**, breaking from the norm in Ireland of looking at risk from sectoral "silos". A participant further stressed that a tool with this level of complexity, bringing together different sectors, would help Ireland begin to address the question of **justice in resilience**.

Participants discussed the importance of platform's case study area as an area that clusters a lot of **key** and **critical infrastructure**, not just for the neighbourhood but for all of Dublin, confirming the need for a platform that will investigate "**chains of impact**" brought about by climatic disturbances and, as a result, allow for more knowledgeable planning. In this regard, one participant highlighted that "decision-makers have to learn everything they can about this area – every decision is worthy of the high stakes that are there."

Participants also argued the tool would help improve the **resilience** of **new housing developments**, given, according to a participant, the limited protocol on building development for flooding. Niall Buckley explained that evacuation needs in Ireland are centred around fire protection and the tool can help **bridge the gap in evacuation protocol** for other climate-induced emergencies.

The discussion on housing resilience amongst participants also revolved around the **Glass Bottle development** in the case study area, a development that will add to Ringsend's current population, despite being in a flood-prone area and generating societal contention. By discussing this development, participants agreed that the tool would help make new housing developments **better prepared** for **climate disturbances**, protecting the people and communities that inhabit them.

Data requirements & inputs

A participant mentioned that including **sustainable drainage systems** (SuDS) could be make the platform even more beneficial, as they mentioned these are not being consistently mapped in Dublin's new developments near the case study area. However, subterranean modelling falls outside the consortium's capacity and expertise, so the focus of the platform will be on buildings and the grid.

Another participant stressed the importance of including lunar patterns to understand flooding. In response, IESRD stressed that **accessibility** of data is a key concern and limitation to the platform, as data sources range in availability and quality across the project's three pilot sites. However, tidal records will be included in the Dublin pilot site.

Multiple participants also mentioned the importance of **wind patterns** as a key driver of environmental damage, particularly on grid infrastructure. In response, IES and the consortium are exploring how to use this type of data, given its importance. However, Niall stressed that inclusion of wind data would

still have limits, as predicting the impact of wind requires an additional level of detailed data on, for example, trees in a neighbourhood, and the use of Computational Fluid Dynamic (CFD) modelling, which falls outside of the scope of the project. Aiming for this detail can “distract from the initial goals of the tool”, therefore, it should not be expected from the final product.

During the discussion the participants validated that **pluvial flooding** is a key concern and data requirement for the Dublin case study area.

Desired data outputs

A participant stressed that an outcome of the platform should be showcasing the **predictability**/probability of climate events and their impact, to allow for more **efficient planning**.

Many participants highlighted the importance of bringing together different models (rainfall, air pressure, tidal patterns) to showcase **knock-on effects** of climate disturbances: “All models have to talk to each other for us to actually get proper answers”.

Target end-users

It was unclear for certain participants who the key end-users of the platform would be. Through discussions with project partners, the end-users were identified as people working in **planning** and **adaptation**, such as those in the room for the workshop. A participant stressed that **decision makers** within these sectors would benefit the most from the platform.

A participant highlighted that the platform should be used by **emergency** and **security services** involved in **major emergency planning**, such as the fire brigade, the army, etc.

A participant raised the question as to whether the technology platform would have a **public interface**. This incited a larger discussion on the inclusion of the public as end-users. One of the key concerns from participants in this regard is that data should be accessible to the public, however, in the case of showcasing risk, it should be accompanied with information on risk mitigation planning. As summarized succinctly by a participant: “providing information with no plan or action is just producing fear without a solution”. The same participant stressed that unless it is related into action, showcasing risk data could do more harm than good. Another participant believed that showing citizens data on risk can, in some circumstances, invigorate them into action for their community, using an example from Derry. It was agreed by most participants that showcasing risks must be done carefully and where there is actual scope for action from community members, without removing the key responsibility from those involved in the protection of the community – decision-makers.

Overall, it was agreed that although interested citizens should have access to the platform the main target audience will remain decision-makers in planning and adaptation sectors and that rather than cater for all needs, the platform excel in visualising risks in the case study’s-built environment to an informed audience.

Key challenges

One key challenge identified by participants and validated by project partners will be how to **communicate** risk in a way that is accessible to planners coming from **different sectors** and **disciplines**.

Another key challenge involves getting powerful stakeholders in the case study area to be aligned with the decisions that the MR tool seeks to facilitate, as well as bringing them into engagement dialogues.

Key limitations

In response to several questions regarding the level of detail provided by the tool in analysing the impacts of risk, it was stressed that since the tool tries to bring in different types of models together with various data inputs, and this field of research and modelling is still underdeveloped, a natural

caveat to the platform will emerge: it will not be able to address all the questions that result from bringing in multiple, distinct models. In other words, there will be a **lack of fidelity** in many of the models. However, it was agreed with participants the tool will still be beneficial by being one of the first of its kind to break out of sectoral silos to understand and identify long-term risk.

2.2.3 Session 2: Critical infrastructure and social vulnerabilities

Map based discussions

In the second discussion session, participants were asked to interact with two printed out maps of the case study area. For the first map (see image 1), participants were asked to identify critical and vulnerable infrastructure according to their personal knowledge and professional expertise on the area.

Image 1: Critical and Vulnerable Infrastructure in Ringsend and Poolbeg

The group identified the following as critical and vulnerable infrastructure in Ringsend and Poolbeg:

- Sewage treatment plant
- Waste-to-Energy facility
- Container area – related to supply chain, therefore immensely critical
- OLD ESB power plant
- Metal Breaking Area
- Pigeon House + surrounding area with hotel

One participant stressed that the north side of the map, referring to the port area north of the River Liffey, is also important, because there is a fuel to the airport from the port. If the south-side gets flooded (case study area), the north will most likely also be flooded – need to consider their concomitance.

Participants stressed the **connected nature** of the key infrastructure points, once again reaffirming the importance of inter-sectoral and inter zone planning to address interconnected risk. An example explained by a participant is the Waste-to-Energy Plant - the fuel source for the new district heating

system. The first client of the district heating system is the Glass Bottle development. If the Waste to Energy facility is flooded, it will have a knock-on effect on the housing at the Glass Bottle site, despite them being physically separate.

For the second map (see image 2), participants were asked to discuss the impacts of disruptive flooding events.

Image 2: Disruptive Flooding Events in Ringsend and Poolbeg

One participant stressed the importance of **Storm Eowyn** (2025) in Ireland’s experience of flood risk management, describing the situation as a “post-humanitarian crisis”. They explained this as being caused by the limited protection available to those affected by the storm. Another participant agreed, recalling how all types of public services including health, shelter, and more, were unavailable to many citizens affected by the storm. Several participants similarly stressed that this storm was crucial for **learnings** for risk management planning, given its severity. Another participant stressed that future events would only be more unprecedented than this storm, therefore, planners need to bridge learnings from the past with future risk projections to truly be well equipped for future impacts.

In discussing the different flooding events that Dublin and, more specifically, the case study area have been affected by, a participant highlighted that most damage from past events was created from things collapsing onto electricity and power lines, thereby causing a chain of disruptive events with wider geographic consequences. Several participants agreed with this reflection, validating the importance of studying the impact of **wind patterns**.

Another participant discussed **Storm Ciara** in Holyhead, UK (2020), and how it impacted the supply chain immensely with consequences felt in Dublin. Participants agreed that this storm served as a reminder to think of the bigger picture on how weather events can have large scale consequences due to the interrelation of many different types of infrastructure, not only nationally but also

internationally. Other events mentioned by participants during the discussion included **Hurricane Charlie** (1986) and a series of unnamed storms affecting Irishtown in 2003.

The reflections on historic flooding events reinforced the key discussion points from session 1 related to the necessity of more **knowledge** about **risk** and better **integrated planning** for risk management.

2.2.4 Session 3: Personal needs and vulnerabilities activity

The final exercise was related to the work from Roman Schotten, University College London (UCL), investigating personal needs and behaviours related to climate-induced emergencies. Participants were numbered and given stickers with their number marked on them. They were then asked to answer three different questions using their numbered stickers. Below, the questions are outlined as well as accompanying discussions that emerged. The visual results of the session can be found in Annex 2.

Question 1: In your professional opinion, which personal needs require most attention in flood risk reduction management in Ringsend, Dublin? *Each participant was allowed to choose 4 answers. Participant answers are displayed in Table 1 (following page).*

Discussion points after the question had been answered:

A participant believed (and others agreed) the option of “**Prevention**” should be a choice as a personal need, as preventing a disaster should be the priority. In response, Roman highlighted that the question should be understood as to prioritise the consequences of events that planners try to prevent.

One participant reflected that the consequences of a flooding event on mental health and well-being often are felt much later after a flooding event, as people usually feel less supported the longer time passes after an event.

Remaining unharmed is a major priority for most participants.

A participant mentioned that although people might say they want to feel like they have a say in decision-making, often what people want in situations of emergency are **leaders**.

Another participant mentioned the importance of considering the impacts of flooding events on communities that are **not directly affected** by the event but might still feel the consequences, for example by not having power, gas, or telecommunication.

Table 1: Personal needs identified by end-users

Answer options	G1 ¹	G2	G3	BE1	BE2	BE3	O1	O2	TOTAL
Having a say in decisions and being involved in society	-	-	-	1	1	-	1	-	3
Accessing news and being able to communicate	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	-	2
Being able to travel and move around freely	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	1
Living in stable social order organized by authorities	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1
Minimising damage to homes and personal belongings	1	-	1	-	-	1	-	1	4
Having emergency services available if needed	1	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	3
Remaining unharmed physically	1	1	1	1	-	-	1	1	6
Getting a stable supply of water and food	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	1	3
Being able to relieve stress and maintain well-being	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
Ensuring the integrity and availability of cultural and religious institutions	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
Accessing water and sanitation services	-	1	-	1	-	1	-	1	4
Being able to make use of medical care and health services	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Accessing workplaces and schools	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1
Having safe shelter and temporary housing available when needed	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	2
Being able to use electricity, heating, or cool	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1

¹ The answers of participants were recorded and are presented here based on the stakeholder category they identified for themselves. G = government, BE = built environment, and O = other.

Question 2: Which personal characteristics should especially be considered for flood risk management efforts in Ringsend, Dublin in general? *Each participant was allowed to choose 3 answers. Participant answers are displayed in Table 2.*

Table 2: Personal Characteristics identified by end-users

Answer options	G1	G2	G3	BE1	BE2	BE3	O1	O2	TOTAL
Physical and mental ability or disability	1	1	1	-	-	-	1	1	5
Financial situation or income level	-	-	1	-	1	1	-	-	3
Family situation	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1
Level of social support or isolation	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	8
Cultural or religious background	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
Migration or refugee experience	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
Household size	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
Housing situation	-	-	-	1	1	1	-	1	4
Employment status	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
Age or life stage	1	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	3
Gender identity	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
Other	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0

Key discussion points after the question had been answered:

Participants stressed that **interconnections** between the categories are important to consider; for example, the financial situation is often linked to level of social support or isolation as well the housing situation.

A participant raised the question whether “disability” is the best word to use, and other participants also discussed the stigma attached to the use of the word vulnerable. They did encourage the project to carefully consider the terminology used, especially when publicly communicating results.

Question 3: Which time and stage of flood risk management is most relevant in Ringsend, Dublin for risk reduction – also in view of more vulnerable groups and personal needs? *Each participant was allowed to choose 2 answers. Participant answers are displayed in Table 3.*

Table 3: Flood risk management time and stage identified by end-users

Answer Options		G1	G2	G3	BE1	BE2	BE3	O1	O2	TOTAL
Response	0 - 3 hours	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
	3 hours – 3 days	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Recovery	weeks	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
	months	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
	years	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	2
Protection and adaptation	months	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
	years	1	-	1	1	1	1	1	1	7
Preparedness	An hour before	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
	Hours before	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
	Days before	-	1	-	1	1	-	1	1	5

Key discussion points after the question had been answered:

Protection and **adaptation** as well as **preparedness** are key – these are what make the response ‘less’ crucial as it mitigates the level of damage for which a response is needed.

Recovery takes years and often is needed in ways that are **overlooked** after initial recovery efforts. A participant stressed that although people might be given support in the initial aftermath of a disaster, in the long term they are in a position of vulnerability that does not warrant immediate support but nonetheless causes immense stress on their lives. For example, the value of their house, their main **asset**, may **decrease considerably** due to flooding impacts and limited or absent insurance coverage, thereby creating long-term doubt about the **financial stability** of their future, affecting other important life choices.

Participants were also asked to provide feedback on the clarity of the questions from a scale of 1 (not clear at all) to 5 (extremely clear). The average response was 3 out of 5, and feedback was given directly to Roman as to how the questions could have been reformulated for better comprehension.

2.2.5 Wrap up and conclusion

To finish the workshop Sabrina Dekker (DCC), Niall Buckley (IES), and Roman Schotten (UCL) were briefly interviewed by Katharina Faradsch about their takeaways of the day and the next steps for their work.

Sabrina reflected from a DCC perspective that the discussion **validated the choice of the DZ as the case study area**, given the high presence of interconnected risks. She encouraged participants to talk to one another, highlighting the importance of keeping discussions on the project and its goals ongoing between individuals, as this is crucial for intersectoral and interdisciplinary collaboration to be successful. For Sabrina, the next steps were focused on the community engagement activity coming up in the afternoon of the same day, and after, focusing on disseminating the results of the workshop(s) to the stakeholders and the wider community through effective communication methods.

Niall stressed that the workshop reminded him of the importance of reflecting on the platform's aims and objectives through potential end-users, to ensure that it is **functional and useful and can deliver the biggest impact**. Niall finished by informing participants that reflections from the workshop and the discussions would be taken back into the project's development team, so the input would be incorporated into the next development stages of the platform.

Roman highlighted that the information from the workshop will help frame his **reflections on the consequences of flooding events and different hazard scenarios**. These will then be integrated into the models being developed. His team will also be looking for more data input in the weeks after the workshop.

2.3 Evaluations

Feedback from participants following the event was highly positive, with consistently strong ratings across key areas. Based on a scale from 0 (very bad) to 5 (very good), the overall quality of the event received an average score of 4. Comments described the workshop as "well-organised," "inclusive," and "a great initiative," with participants particularly appreciating the "open, good discussion," the "sticker activity and questions," and the opportunity for "cross-sectoral learning."

The extent to which the event met its objectives was also rated at 4, indicating broad satisfaction, though with slightly more variation. Some participants expressed curiosity about the project's next steps - one noted, "I'm curious what comes out of it," and another commented, "It will be interesting to hear the results of the workshop with the citizens," referring to the community workshop taking place later that day. These responses suggest a need for clearer communication on follow-up actions and the overall impact pathway in future workshops.

The composition of the participant group was rated positively (4.1), with many respondents indicating it supported the achievement of the workshop's aims. The opportunity to contribute to discussions was rated particularly high (4.8), with nearly all participants giving it a score of 5. The open and inclusive format was widely appreciated, with several attendees valuing the chance to engage across sectors and communities.

Regarding knowledge gained, the workshop was ranked an average of 4.1 in its ability to develop insights relevant to participants' work. While most participants found the content insightful - especially in relation to the Ringsend area - some felt it could be more tailored to their specific contexts.

Finally, logistical and technical arrangements received high ratings (4.2), reflecting the good organisation. One key area for improvement was clarity of messaging, echoed in the concise suggestion to "keep the message simple." This will be an important takeaway for shaping future engagement activities.

The full evaluation can be found in Annex 3.

3 Community Engagement

3.1 Event details

The engagement with community members of the Ringsend and Poolbeg case study area took place at the Ringsend and Irishtown Community Centre on 14 May 2025, between 4.00 and 8.00 pm. The event took the form of a small, outdoor community festival. Different activities were spread out in the outside area of the community centre, including two stands for the MR project being hosted by relevant researchers and supported by other attending partners. Other activities, particularly targeted at kids, included face painting and potting plants. Free ice-cream, snacks, and beverages were provided to all. Passers-by were welcomed into the community centre area and encouraged to participate.

The event was organized by Dublin City Council (DCC) in close collaboration with Prospex Institute (PI) and contributions from Trinity College Dublin (TCD) und University College London (UCL). All organisations are partners in the Minority Report project.

A total of 20 community members participated in the activities and a lot more passed by the community festival and informed themselves about the project.

3.2 Personal needs and vulnerabilities

One of the stands of the community fair was hosted by Roman Schotten, from UCL, investigating personal needs and behaviours related to climate-induced emergencies. As with the end-user workshop, participants were asked to answer three different questions. However, to minimize the risk of bias based on previous answers, it was decided to not use stickers on the posters but rather record the answers via an online survey. The survey was completed by a supporting project partner while the participant answered the questions. Below, the questions are outlined with the answers from participants. A total of 13 citizens participated in the activity.

Question 1: In your personal opinion, which human personal needs require most attention in flood risk reduction management in Ringsend, Dublin? *Each participant was allowed to choose 4 answers. Participant answers are displayed in Table 4.*

Table 4: Personal needs identified by community members

Answer Options	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	TOTAL
Having a say in decisions and being involved in society	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
Accessing news and being able to communicate	1	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
Being able to travel and move around freely	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	2
Living in stable social order organized by authorities	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Minimizing damage to homes and personal belongings	-	1	-	-	1	-	1	-	1	1	-	1	1	7
Having emergency services available if needed	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	3
Remaining unharmed physically	-	1	-	1	1	-	-	-	1	1	1	-	1	7
Getting a stable supply of water and food	-	-	1	1	-	1	1	1	-	1	1	1	1	9
Being able to relieve stress and maintain well-being	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	2
Ensuring the integrity and availability of cultural and religious institutions	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	2
Accessing water and sanitation services	-	1	1	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	1	1	6
Being able to make use of medical care and health services	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
Accessing workplaces and schools	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Having safe shelter and temporary housing available when needed	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	1	1	1	-	-	5
Being able to use electricity, heating, or cool	-	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3

Question 2: Which personal characteristics should especially be considered for flood risk management efforts in Ringsend, Dublin in general? *Each participant was allowed to choose 3 answers. Participant answers are displayed in Table 5.*

Table 5: Personal characteristics identified by community members

Answer Options	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	TOTAL
Physical and mental ability or disability	1	1	1	1	1	-	1	1	1	1	1	1	-	11
Financial situation or income level	1	-	1	1	-	1	-	-	-	1	1	-	1	7
Family situation	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	3
Level of social support or isolation	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	4
Cultural or religious background	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Migration or refugee experience	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Household size	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1
Housing situation	-	1	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	1	1	-	-	5
Employment status	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1
Age or life stage	-	-	1	-	1	1	1	1	-	-	-	1	-	6
Gender identity	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Question 3: Which time and stage of flood risk management is most relevant in Ringsend, Dublin for risk reduction – also in view of more vulnerable groups and personal needs? *Each participant was allowed to choose 2 answers. Participant answers are displayed in Table 6.*

Table 6: Flood risk management time and stage identified by community members

Answer Options		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	TOTAL
Response	0 - 3 hours	1	-	-	-	1	1	1	-	-	-	1	-	-	5
	3 hours – 3 days	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
Recovery	weeks	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	2
	months	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1
	years	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	-	2
Protection and adaptation	months	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	2
	years	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
Preparedness	An hour before	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Hours before	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Days before	-	1	1	-	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	-	10

3.3 Lived experiences

The second stand at the community festival was hosted by Dimitra Xidou and Thomas Grey from Trinity College Dublin (TCD). Participants could participate in either of two activities: the daily clock canvas and/ or mapping the neighbourhood. For the daily clock canvas, participants were asked to colour in a printed out daily clock according to their **daily routines**, thereby creating a visual record of where and how they spent time in the case study area’s-built environment over a 24h period (see Annex 5 for scans of the daily clocks). The second activity involved citizen **mapping** of the case study area. Participants were asked to mark what they considered to be the approximate **boundary** of the neighbourhood and describe the **main spatial components** within it (see Annex 6 for the visual outcome of the activity). Lastly, certain participants were asked to take ‘diaries’ home with them and complete them over the course of a week. Through these diaries, participants would provide a longer narrative account of their routines and behaviours, further complementing the data collected from the daily clocks and the maps.

Through the combination of all three activities, TCD will be able to gain a better understanding of citizens **lived experiences** within the case study area, allowing for the informed ‘**co-creation**’ of ‘personas’ integrated in the MR tool. These personas will mimic key **stakeholder behaviours** during emergency weather events, allowing for more efficient response planning that reflects the reality of different citizens. A total of 15 participant daily clocks were completed, 8 entries collected on the map, and 3 diaries were provided.

3.4 Key learnings

Partners involved in organising the event considered the event an overall success, due, in part, to the balanced demographic reach of the event regarding participant **age** and **gender**. Citizens of all ages

engaged in the different activities, ensuring that a **diverse representation** of perspectives across these dimensions can be integrated into the project's research. Additionally, partners felt there was a strong level of **curiosity** from community members on the project and its goals, coupled with a general **openness** for discussion. This not only allows the project to gain exposure within the case study's community but also helps initiate a long-term process of **trust-building** between citizens and the project.

Key learnings also emerged for future citizen engagement activities. Despite the general balance of participants regarding age and gender, it was agreed by partners that the event would have benefitted from increased visibility of **different vulnerable** social groups within Ringsend and Poolbeg. For future events, organising partners should send **targeted invitations** to key stakeholder groups in advance of any planned activities to ensure their **participation** and **inclusion** within the research being developed. Additionally, from a logistical standpoint, hosting activities closer to the street and its sidewalk would increase exposure to passers-by and improve participation rates.

4 Annex

4.1 Agenda of end-user workshop

 MINORITY
REPORT

Agenda

- 11:00 – 11:30** Welcome and Introduction
- 11:30 – 12:15** *Discussion Session 1:*
Interaction with and views on MR tool
- 12:15 – 12:55** *Discussion Session 2:*
Needs, vulnerabilities and critical infrastructure
- 12:55 – 13:00** Wrap up and next steps

4 |

4.2 Visual results of end-user workshop discussion

MINORITY REPORT Question 3a

In your professional opinion which personal needs require most attention in flood risk reduction management in Ringsend, Dublin?

Please read all options and then place your 4 stickers on or next to the icon of the personal needs you choose. You can place all 4 on one personal need if wanted or spread your stickers.

Being able to relieve stress and maintain well-being	
Ensuring the integrity and availability of cultural and religious institutions.	
Accessing water and sanitation services	
Being able to make use of medical care and health services	
Accessing workplaces and schools	
Having safe shelter and temporary housing available when needed	
Being able to use electricity, heating or cooling	
Getting a stable supply of water and food	

Q3a

Poster on Question 1 with results

MINORITY REPORT

Which personal characteristics should especially be considered for flood risk management efforts in Ringsend, Dublin in general?

Poster on Question 2 with results

Poster on Question 3 with results

4.3 Full participant evaluation of the end-user workshop

How do you rate the quality of the workshop in general?

8 out of 9 answered

4.0 Average rating

To what extent did the workshop reach the set objectives?

8 out of 9 answered

4.0 Average rating

Was the composition of the group of participants beneficial to the aim and objectives of the event?

8 out of 9 answered

4.1 Average rating

To what extent did you feel enabled to contribute to the discussion?

8 out of 9 answered

4.8 Average rating

Were you able to develop insights and knowledge relevant for you and your work?

8 out of 9 answered

4.1 Average rating

How do you rate the quality of the presentations?

8 out of 9 answered

4.2 Average rating

How would you rate the work of the facilitator(s)?

8 out of 9 answered

4.5 Average rating

How would you rate the practical, logistical and / or technical arrangements?

8 out of 9 answered

4.2 Average rating

4.4 Neighbourhood map from the community engagement

4.5 Daily clocks created during the community engagement

See pages 30 – 44. Please note some sections of the daily clocks have been redacted to maintain anonymity of participants.

Daily clock: understanding how we interact with the built environment throughout the day

Use a different colour for each segment, or a group of segments, to show mainly where you are for those hours:

yellow=at home (or equivalent)	
orange=workplace/school/college etc	
green=3rd place (e.g. gym, cafe, club)	
red=out in the community, in public space, on public transport, in the car, etc	
blue= other (defined by respondent)	

Key information

Neighbourhood being discussed:

Some information about you

- Age:
- Gender: M / F / Non-binary / prefer not to say
- Occupation:
- Any long-term condition or impairment:
- How long have you been living, or frequently spending time in this neighbourhood:
- Have you experienced a climate-related or natural disaster event in this area: Y/ N
- If Yes, what was this:

When was this:

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Daily clock: understanding how we interact with the built environment throughout the day

Use a different colour for each segment, or a group of segments, to show mainly where you are for those hours:

- yellow=at home (or equivalent)
- orange=workplace/school/college etc
- green=3rd place (e.g. gym, cafe, club)
- red=out in the community, in public space, on public transport, in the car, etc
- blue= other (defined by respondent)

Key information

Neighbourhood being discussed:

playing out

Some information about you

- Age:
 - Gender: M / F / Non-binary / prefer not to say
 - Occupation: *student*
 - Any long-term condition or impairment: *NO*
 - How long have you been living, or frequently spending time in this neighbourhood: *my whole life*
 - Have you experienced a climate-related or natural disaster event in this area: Y/ N
 - If Yes, what was this: *It snowed*
- When was this:

Daily clock: understanding how we interact with the built environment throughout the day

Use a different colour for each segment, or a group of segments, to show mainly where you are for those hours:

- yellow=at home (or equivalent)
- orange=workplace/ school/college etc
- green=3rd place (e.g. gym, cafe, club)
- red=out in the community, in public space, on public transport, in the car, etc
- blue= other (defined by respondent)

Key information

Neighbourhood being discussed:

Some information about you

- Age: 11
- Gender: M / F / Non-binary / prefer not to say
- Occupation: Student
- Any long-term condition or impairment: No
- How long have you been living, or frequently spending time in this neighbourhood: 10 years
- Have you experienced a climate-related or natural disaster event in this area: Y/ N
- If Yes, what was this: When it snowed
- When was this:

Playing out

Not on map

Daily clock: understanding how we interact with the built environment throughout the day

Use a different colour for each segment, or a group of segments, to show mainly where you are for those hours:

- yellow=at home (or equivalent)
- orange=workplace/school/college etc
- green=3rd place (e.g. gym, cafe, club)
- red=out in the community, in public space, on public transport, in the car, etc
- blue= other (defined by respondent)

Key information

Neighbourhood being discussed:

Some information about you

- Age: 62
- Gender: M / F / Non-binary / prefer not to say
- Occupation: [REDACTED]
- Any long-term condition or impairment: [REDACTED]
- How long have you been living, or frequently spending time in this neighbourhood: [REDACTED]
- Have you experienced a climate-related or natural disaster event in this area? Y/N
- If Yes, what was this: STORM (January 2025) FLOODING
- When was this: [REDACTED]

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• had the house red - storm - we stayed but the storm in 2025 - the whole inclusion, the red was built for a different time.

11 yr old girl

Daily clock: understanding how we interact with the built environment throughout the day

Use a different colour for each segment, or a group of segments, to show mainly where you are for those hours:

- yellow=at home (or equivalent)
- orange=workplace/school/college etc
- green=3rd place (e.g. gym, cafe, club)
- red=out in the community, in public space, on public transport, in the car, etc
- blue= other (defined by respondent)

Key information
Neighbourhood being discussed:

- Some information about you
- Age: 11
 - Gender: ~~M~~ / (F) Non-binary / prefer not to say
 - Occupation: student
 - Any long-term condition or impairment:
 - How long have you been living, or frequently spending time in this neighbourhood:
 - Have you experienced a climate-related or natural disaster event in this area: Y/ N
 - If Yes, what was this: 103
 - When was this: yesterday

Daily clock: understanding how we interact with the built environment throughout the day

Use a different colour for each segment, or a group of segments, to show mainly where you are for those hours:

- yellow=at home (or equivalent)
- orange=workplace/school/college etc
- green=3rd place (e.g. gym, cafe, club)
- red=out in the community, in public space, on public transport, in the car, etc
- blue= other (defined by respondent)

Key information

Neighbourhood being discussed:

Some information about you

- Age: 36
- Gender: M / F / Non-binary / prefer not to say
- Occupation: XXXXXXXXXX
- Any long-term condition or impairment: no
- How long have you been living, or frequently spending time in this neighbourhood: XXXXXXXXXX
- Have you experienced a climate-related or natural disaster event in this area: Y/N
- If Yes, what was this:

When was this: *opnetia, Big Snow*

9!

floody in biggest concern

lack of water infrastructure in Ireland

↳ this is a huge issue

and also water-facility

but no impact

5

Daily clock: understanding how we interact with the built environment throughout the day

Use a different colour for each segment, or a group of segments, to show mainly where you are for those hours:

- yellow=at home (or equivalent)
- orange=workplace/school/college etc
- green=3rd place (e.g. gym, cafe, club)
- red=out in the community, in public space, on public transport, in the car, etc
- blue= other (defined by respondent)

Key information

Neighbourhood being discussed:

Some information about you

- Age: *61*
- Gender: M / F / Non-binary / prefer not to say *F*

- Occupation:

- Any long-term condition or impairment:

- How long have you been living, or frequently spending time in this neighbourhood: *19 + years*

- Have you experienced a climate-related or natural disaster event in this area: Y/N

- If Yes, what was this: *1999*

When was this: *1999 - Flooding @ Dodder*

*C. (gave her a diary).

Not on map.

- we live in an estate but don't have our own garden, so can't (at the moment) do it.
- want to invest in a good electric bike but want to keep it secure.

Daily clock: understanding how we interact with the built environment throughout the day

Use a different colour for each segment, or a group of segments, to show mainly where you are for those hours:

- yellow=at home (or equivalent)
- orange=workplace/school/college etc
- green=3rd place (e.g. gym, cafe, club)
- red=out in the community, in public space, on public transport, in the car, etc
- blue= other (defined by respondent)

Key information

Neighbourhood being discussed:

Some information about you

- Age:
- Gender: M / F / Non-binary / prefer not to say
- Occupation:
- Any long-term condition or impairment:
- How long have you been living, or frequently spending time in this neighbourhood:
- Have you experienced a climate-related or natural disaster event in this area: Y/ N
- If Yes, what was this:
- When was this:

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- walk from home -

Daily clock: understanding how we interact with the built environment throughout the day

Use a different colour for each segment, or a group of segments, to show mainly where you are for those hours:

- yellow=at home (or equivalent)
- orange=workplace/school/college etc
- green=3rd place (e.g. gym, cafe, club)
- red=out in the community, in public space, on public transport, in the car, etc
- blue= other (defined by respondent)

Key information

Neighbourhood being discussed:

Some information about you

- Age: 46
- Gender: M / F / Non-binary / prefer not to say
- Occupation: XXXXXXXXXX
- Any long-term condition or impairment: NO
- How long have you been living, or frequently spending time in this neighbourhood: XXXXXXXXXX
- Have you experienced a climate-related or natural disaster event in this area: Y / N Y
- If Yes, what was this: FLOODING 1999 / SINK HOLE 1978

Daily clock: understanding how we interact with the built environment throughout the day

Use a different colour for each segment, or a group of segments, to show mainly where you are for those hours:

- yellow=at home (or equivalent)
- orange=workplace/school/college etc
- green=3rd place (e.g. gym, cafe, club)
- red=out in the community, in public space, on public transport, in the car, etc
- blue= other (defined by respondent)

Key information

Neighbourhood being discussed:

Some information about you

- Age: 25
- Gender: M / F / Non-binary / prefer not to say
- Occupation:
- Any long-term condition or impairment:
- How long have you been living, or frequently spending time in this neighbourhood:
- Have you experienced a climate-related or natural disaster event in this area: Y *storm*
- If Yes, what was this:
- When was this:

6

Daily clock: understanding how we interact with the built environment throughout the day

Use a different colour for each segment, or a group of segments, to show mainly where you are for those hours:

- yellow=at home (or equivalent)
- orange=workplace/school/college etc
- green=3rd place (e.g. gym, cafe, club)
- red=out in the community, in public space, on public transport, in the car, etc
- blue= other (defined by respondent)

Key information

Neighbourhood being discussed:

Some information about you

- Age:
- Gender: M / F / Non-binary / prefer not to say
- Occupation:
- Any long-term condition or impairment:
- How long have you been living, or frequently spending time in this neighbourhood:
- Have you experienced a climate-related or natural disaster event in this area: Y/ N
- If Yes, what was this:
- When was this:

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Daily clock: understanding how we interact with the built environment throughout the day

Use a different colour for each segment, or a group of segments, to show mainly where you are for those hours

yellow=at home (or equivalent)

orange=workplace/school/college etc

green=3rd place (e.g. gym, cafe, club)

red=out in the community, in public space, on public transport, in the car, etc

blue= other (defined by respondent)

Key information

Neighbourhood being discussed:

Some information about you

- Age: 64
- Gender: M / F / Non-binary / prefer not to say
- Occupation: [REDACTED]
- Any long-term condition or impairment: NO
- How long have you been living, or frequently spending time in this neighbourhood: [REDACTED]
- Have you experienced a climate-related or natural disaster event in this area: Y / N
- If Yes, what was this: flooding
- When was this: 1999

4

Daily clock: understanding how we interact with the built environment throughout the day

Use a different colour for each segment, or a group of segments, to show where you are for those hours.

yellow=at home (or equivalent)

orange=workplace/school/college etc

green=3rd place (e.g. gym, cafe, club)

red=out in the community, in public space, on public transport, in the car, etc

blue= other (defined by respondent)

I use PUBLIC Transport 4 buses daily

Key information

Neighbourhood being discussed:

Some information about you

- Age: *50's*
- Gender: M / F / Non-binary / prefer not to say
- Occupation: [Redacted]
- Any long-term condition or impairment: *no.*
- How long have you been living, or frequently spend [Redacted]

natural disaster event in this area? *Y/N*

- If Yes, what was this:

When was this: *Floating wind damage Shortage of water.*

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TrinityHaus
www.tcd.ie/trinityhaus

Mitigating environmental disruptive events using people-centric predictive digital technologies to improve disaster and climate resilience

www.minorityreport-project.eu/en/

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